

Modelling Energy Demand from Air Conditioning in Households Using MAED - Suriname Case Study

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Context

- Climate control systems account for approximately 40% of a building's energy consumption.

Research questions:

- What is the energy demand from air conditioning systems in the households of Suriname?
- How much energy can be saved when following energy efficiency policy standards for cooling appliances?

WorldAtlas. (2021). *Suriname Maps & Facts*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldatlas.com/maps/suriname>.

MAED D

MAED Model for Analysis of Energy Demand

MAED D ▼ About ?

General information

Name of the case study **Suriname Household Air Conditioning - Baseline Scenario**

Definitions (name, years, description)

Name of the case study
Suriname Household Air Conditioning - Baseline Scenario

Years
2019,2020,2021,2022,2023,2024,2025,2026,2027,2028,2029,2030,21

Case description
This analysis will focus on the final energy demand of air conditioning in the household sector of Suriname's urban districts Paramaribo and Wanica

Units

Population
 Thousand Million

GDP
 Million [10⁶] Billion [10⁹] US Dollar ▼
 Trillion [10¹²]

Transport Passenger (pkm)
 Million [10⁶] Billion [10⁹] Trillion [10¹²]

Transport Freight (tkm)
 Million [10⁶] Billion [10⁹] Trillion [10¹²]

Energy unit
 GWyr PJ Tcal Mtoe
 GBTU

Sectors & Clients

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Challenges

- No reports found indicating the number of households for each urban and rural district in Suriname.
- The percentage of households in Suriname with installed and working air conditioners was not recorded after 2018.
- No research found on the average COP of air conditioners in various types of dwellings in Suriname.

The screenshot displays the MAED Model for Analysis of Energy Demand interface. The main title is "Energy intensities" for the case study "Suriname Household Air Conditioning - Baseline Scenario". The interface is set to "Urban" mode. A table shows data for the years 2019 through 2023, with a final column for 202. The table includes categories such as "Paramaribo & Wanica", "Shares by dwelling type", "Dwelling sizes by dwelling type", "Dwelling Factors for Air Conditioning", and "Specific cooling requirements".

Item	Unit	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	202
Paramaribo & Wanica							
Shares by dwelling type							
Residential building	%	100.00000	100.00000	100.00000	100.00000	100.00000	100.00000
Dwelling sizes by dwelling type							
Residential building	m2	150.00000	150.00000	150.00000	150.00000	150.00000	150.00000
Dwelling Factors for Air Conditioning							
Dwelling with air conditioning							
Residential building	%	33.91000	34.11000	34.31000	34.51000	34.71000	34.91000
Specific cooling requirements							
Residential building	kWh/dw/yr	1699.20000	1243.20000	1749.20000	1620.00000	1636.08000	1651.92000

Approach

- Simulate the energy demand from air conditioning in households from Suriname’s urban districts Paramaribo and Wanica.
- Develop three baseline scenarios in MAED using various growth rates for the future percentage of households with air conditioners.
- Air conditioners in each baseline scenario type (Baseline Low/Mid/High) have a COP of 3.52.

Scenarios

An Efficient Cooling Scenario and an IEA Scenario are then simulated in MAED for each baseline scenario type in order to determine their energy demand and energy savings.

Scenario Label	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Efficient Cooling Scenario	In this scenario energy efficiency policy standards for cooling appliances are introduced in 2025.	Existing air conditioners are replaced with COP 4.0 air conditioners starting 2025.
IEA Scenario	This scenario is based on the IEA's estimation for the average efficiency of new air conditioners in the Net Zero Scenario.	Existing air conditioners are replaced by air conditioners with a COP of 4.8 in 2025, followed by air conditioners with a COP of 5.5 in 2030.

Results (1/2)

Final Energy Demand for Air Conditioning in Urban Households of Suriname (GWyr)

Final Energy Demand for Air Conditioning in Urban Households of Suriname (GWyr)

Final Energy Demand for Air Conditioning in Urban Households of Suriname (GWyr)

Results (2/2)

Conclusions and Policy Insights

The results of the MAED simulation show the following:

- The annual energy demand from air conditioners in the households of Paramaribo and Wanica are at minimum 0.00184 GW (16,118,400 kWh).
- The IEA Scenario saves more energy for each baseline scenario type than the Efficient Cooling Scenario, with average annual savings of 0.000526 GW (4,607,760 kWh) or more between 2025 and 2029, and 0.000797 GW (6,981,720 kWh) or more between 2030 and 2033.

The IEA scenario however requires existing air conditioners to be replaced every five years with more efficient air conditioners. Given Suriname's economic situation, it is unclear whether this scenario will be financially feasible for residential customers unless the government implements policies to assist residents in replacing their air conditioners.

Future Work

Modelling the Energy Demand for all Sectors in Suriname using MAED.